

Original Research

Electronic Human Resource Management (e-HRM) and Organisational Performance

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Abstract

This study was carried out to examine employees' perception of the effect of electronic human resource management (e-HRM) on organizational performance. Focused on four e-HRM components: e-recruitment, e-training, e-performance system, e-compensation combined effect on organizational performance (financial, customers, internal business, learning/growth) and determined the component with the strongest effect. Questionnaire survey covering demographics, e-HRM components and organizational performance on 332 respondents drawn from middle to senior level management employees of two Brewery firms in South-West Nigeria. Questions were framed to assess the extent to which they agree or disagree with the use and effect of e-HRM on organizational performance. Data collected was analysed using inferential statistical techniques of Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Modelling to test the significance of e-HRM on organizational performance. Respondents perceived e-HRM improved organizational performance. Model $\beta = 0.690$, $t = 17.491$, $f^2 = 0.910$, predicted that $P < 0.05$ up to 48% variation in organisational performance is explained by e-HRM practices. Weight of each component showed: e-Recruitment= 0.383, e-Training= 0.078, e-Performance System= 0.216, e-Compensation= 0.250 as e-recruitment is perceived to have the strongest weight and effect on organizational performance. Implication is that the organisations should strengthen e-Recruitment exercise and strategically position e-HRM practices as corporate strategies to enhance organization performance.

Keywords: e-HRM, e-recruitment, e-training, e-performance, e-compensation, organisational performance.

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Introduction

Human resource management has been of significant development in the field of management for the strategic importance of employees which are resources to organisations. The approach in managing employees within organisations have experienced a paradigm shift as organisations now utilize digital technologies in human resource management activities. For values to be delivered within the organisations, HR professionals need to be aware of the shift in practices within human resource management, as driven by technology innovations that has led to electronic human resource management (e-HRM). It has been observed that e-HRM is increasingly seen as having the capacity to contribute to organizational strategic goals which in turn becomes a predictor to organizational outcomes and performance (Bondarouk, & Ruel, 2009; Parry, 2011).

The increase in number of personnel and the need to manage them in fulfilling organisational strategic goals calls for attention within the corporate organisations. In the present context of digitalisations, organisations and their environs have become increasingly complex as human resource managers in these organisations face growing difficulties, of how to tap the right talents, cope with existing workforces that are spread across various departments, systems, cultures, regions and countries in their large sizes (Ahmed, 2019). Organisations are becoming more complex because of the increase in their information management needs (Parry, 2011). The growing significance of human resource management, size of the organisations, changes in economies, maintenance of employee related data and generation of information reports for strategic development within organisations and concerns for HR professionals (Adelekan, 2016).

Meanwhile, it has been empirically found, that traditional methods lack the capability to capture employees' attendance, productivity and performance in real time. Given such trends, manual and traditional human resource management practices in recruitment, training, performance management systems and compensation, are completely inadequate (Adelekan, 2016; Ahmed, 2019). Over the years, organisations have moved from human resource management practices (HRMP) to strategic human resource management (SHRM) to curtail the global challenges. Despite this, the challenges of human resources globally still persist and this has led to the adoption of e-HRM by some organisations which is believed might solve the human resources management related challenges. A few discussions exist in the academic literature about the potential goals of e-HRM, but few scholars have looked at whether these goals are actually realised and which factors have an impact on them to affect the performance of organisation. Whereas, e-HRM is gaining importance with its inherent advantages but there is a lack of clarity regarding the contribution of e-HRM to HR service delivery, employees and effects on organisational performance. These have revealed various lack of perception and empirical studies in literature (Bondarouk & Ruel, 2009; Bondarouk, Parry & Furtmueller, 2017).

Few studies in Nigeria have also shown, that relationship exist between e-HRM and organisational performance but with identified gaps (Abiodun *et al.* 2013; Ahmed, 2019). E-HRM application in the corporate organisations is an emerging idea in

developing countries as corporate organisations now leverage on the strategic importance of e-HRM in its components level of e-training, e-compensation, e-performance management system, e-recruitment to attain organizational performance (Abiodun *et al.*, 2013; Ahmed, 2019). The employees within the organization are exposed to the use of these e-HRM applications as it related to their daily jobs. It is in view of this that this study provided an answer to a research question: what is the employees perception of the effect of e-HRM on organisational performance in the Nigerian Brewery industry?

Literature Review

Electronic Human Resource Management (e-HRM)

Review of existing literatures shows the growing attempts on researchers to find an acceptable definition to the novel but progressively growing concept of e-HRM. Strohmeier (2007) described e-HRM as the planning, implementation and application of information technology for both networking and supporting at least two individual or collective actors in their shared performing of HR activities. Ruel, Bondarouk and Looise (2004), also defined e-HRM as ‘a way of implementing HRM strategies, policies, and practices in organisations through the conscious and direct support of and/or with the full use of channels based on web-technologies. Bondarouk and Ruel (2009), described e-HRM as “An umbrella term covering all possible integration mechanism and contents between HRM and information technologies, aimed at creating value for targeted employees and managers”. E-HRM has further been seen as an enterprise-wide strategy that uses scalable, flexible, and integrated technology to link internal processes and knowledge workers directly to the business objectives of the organisation. Voermans and Van Veldhoven (2007), Bondarouk and Ruel, (2009) opined that, e-HRM could narrowly be defined as administrative support of the HR functions in organisations by using internet technology which can be an integration of People, Process and Technology which uses web-based technology to carry out the HR functions within the organisations. The organization explores the components of e-HRM in e-recruitment, e-training, e-performance system, e-compensation to enhance the traditional practices. *e-Recruitment* could be described as the strategic and extensive use of digital technology or web-based technological tool to assist the recruitment process of an organization. *e-Training* is the use of digital technologies to train employees of the organisation. *e-Performance management system* may be defined as a system in which electronic technology is integrated with the performance management process of the organization in order to improve individual and team performance in the organisation. *e-Compensation* is the integration of digital technology tools for managing the salary structure to drive performance. These identified components are being accomplished in different ways within the organization which are referred to as types of e-HRM.

Operational e-HRM

consists the basic administrative activities of the HR department, such as personnel data management, departmental records and others. Authors have supported this to have increased efficiency created by e-HRM which minimizes HR staff bounded to these activities. (Ruel, *et al.*, 2004; Strohmeier, 2007). Operational e-HRM brings efficiency

by a way of reducing overhead costs, enhancing the accuracy of data, eliminating the costs of printing and disseminating information, minimizing IT infrastructure costs by moving towards a common HR service platform and enhancing the ability to distribute HR information and services globally.

Relational e-HRM

comprises those HR activities that support a mutual relationship between the HR department and other departments within the organisation. These type of e-HRM activities include functions such as e-recruitment, e-training and e-performance management. Relational e-HRM may provide employees and managers with remote access to HR information, thus increasing their ability to connect with other internal and external stakeholders, as well as providing individuals with the tools to perform HR activities themselves. Swaroop, (2012) opined that, relational e-HRM brings relational impact to the organisation by changing the nature of the relationship between HR, line managers and employees.

Transformational e-HRM

focuses on the combination of relational e-HRM and strategic activities of HRM, such as organisational change processes, strategic re-orientation and strategic competence management. It has been opined that, by improving the strategic orientation of HRM, e-HRM has the capacity to transform the HR function (Ruel *et al.*, 2004). A strategic HR function links HRM activities to the strategic management process and strategic objectives of the organisation. This leads to an integrated set of policies and practices developed to execute the company's implicit or explicit business strategy through the management of the organisation's human resources (Wright, Dunford & Snell, 2001). Moreover, (Swaroop,2012) further explained that, transformational e-HRM brings a level of impact by transforming HR's role into that of a strategic business partner, adding greater value to the business by increasing HR's influence as customer focused. A strategic goal of e-HRM is then to contribute to the strategic alignment of the HRM function.(Ghazzawi & Accoume, 2014).

Organisational performance (OP)

Derinney; Johnson and Yip (2009) described organisational performance as an ultimate dependent variable of interest for researchers concerned with any area of management. Organisational performance lies at the heart of a firm's survival and is recognized as a strategic outcome variable (Singh, Darwish & Potocnik, 2016). This refers to how well an organization achieves its goals and objectives. A broad concept that captures the efficiency and effectiveness with which an organization utilizes its resources, meets its strategic goals, satisfies stakeholders, and sustains itself over time. OP has been defined as asset of both financial and non-financial indicators capable of assessing the degree to which organisational corporate vision have been accomplished (Kaplan & Norton, 1996). An approach of measurement in Balanced Score Card (BSC) model on organisational performance is reviewed and utilized in this study (Kaplan & Norton, 1996; Ibrahim & Lloyd, 2011). BSC provides a quick and comprehensive view of the entire business process by using a set of balanced measures from four different

perspectives of, financial perspective; Customer perspective; Internal perspective; Learning and Growth perspective (Ibrahim & Lloyd, 2011)

The financial perspective represents the long- term goal of the organisations- to provide superior returns on investment (Hussain &Farooq, 2011; Kaplan & Norton, 1996). The customer perspective represents measures that depends on the type of customers desired and the value the organisation provides to them. This will allow organisations to create strategic measure with the type of customers they want to attract and retain. (Nalwoga & Dijk, 2016) The internal business perspective according to (Kaplan & Norton, 1996) entails the procedures that an organisations must develop and master to be successful. This reflects the concentration on elements like product innovation. Whereas, the learning and growth perspective is the backbone to a successful scorecard because it involves employee skills, satisfaction and capacity (Kaplan & Norton, 1996).

Theory Underpinning

This study is underpinned with Adaptive Structuration Theory (AST) originated from Anthony Gidden’s structuration theory in 1984. The structuration theory was formulated as the production and reproduction of the social sytems through members use of rules and resources in iterraction. DeSanctis and Poole (1994) adapted Giddens' theory to study the interaction of groups and organisations with information technology and called it “Adapted Structuration Theory”. AST is useful in providing an understanding of how the structures that are created in groups influence communication and decisions, which is useful in examining the role that power plays in the development of groups and in the accomplishment of their goals.

DeSanctis and Poole, (1994) further opined that, it is important not only to understand the existence of resources but also to examine how these resources evolve and change as a result of the communication activity that takes place within the group in making decisions. Ruel, Magalhaes and Chiemeke (2007) stated that AST was developed for studying groups which were using an electronic group decision support system which also support the usage of computer systems and the nature of group-computer interaction.

AST is relevant to this study due to the expanding influence that digital technologies have had with regard to the human-computer interaction and its implications on socio-biologically inspired structuration in security software applications. De Sanctis and Poole (1994) explained that, AST provides a model that describes the interplay between advanced information technologies, social structures, and human interaction.

Empirical Review

Rahman and Hosain (2021) studied E-HRM Practices for Organisational Sustainability: Evidence from Selected Textile Firms in Bagladesh. The study was carried out to ascertain the relationship between five e-HRM practices as independent variables, e-recruitment and e-selection, e-training, e-performance management, e-compensation, e-communication and organizational sustainability as dependent

variable, measured through profit and market growth. The Quantitative primary data was through questionnaire while the secondary data was from the organisations annual reports using Pearsons correlation and regression analysis in SPSS24 for data analysis. The findings revealed that e-HRM had significant positive relationship with the dependent variables, Organisational Sustainability, which showed a reducing operational cost and increase profit. Thathsaru and Sutha, (2021), investigated the influence of e-HRM practices on Organizational Performance, the mediating role of organizational agility in a study. The research instrument used was questionnaire using covariance sampling method to collect data from 40 financial institutions in Sri Lanka. Analysis was carried out using correlation, regression, descriptive statistics, Baron and Kenny mediator analysis method and Sobel test to examine the mediating role of organisational agility. The result showed that e-HRM significantly and positively improved organizational performance while organization agility mediates the relationship between e-HRM practices and organisational performance.

Obama, Kyongo, Munithis, and Amata, (2020) examined the effects of electronic human resource management practices on Organisational performance: A Case of University of Maryland Programs, Nairobi Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive research design having used stratified sampling technique with a sample size of 107. Primary data was used with questionnaire as the research instrument. The findings revealed that 88.7% of the respondents were aware that e-compensation was utilized to a large extent and 84.1% were aware that e-recruitment was used within the institution. The results showed that e-recruitment, e-training, e-compensation had significant effect on organisational flexibility and effectiveness. The results further showed that e-performance was the most significant of all the components of e-HRM to organisational effectiveness. Ahmed (2019) found that positive relationship exists between e-HRM variables and organisational performance variables in an empirical research work on the impact of e-HRM practices on organisational performance in manufacturing industries in Bangladesh. The study examined six dimensions of performance which includes among others, efficiencies, effectiveness and quality and used nine components of e-HRM, which includes among others e-recruitment, e-training, e-compensation. The quantitative study with the use of questionnaire had a sample of 223 employees within the manufacturing industry in Bangladesh. Findings revealed a significant effect of e-HRM on organizational performance.

Meanwhile, in Nigeria studies like Abiodun, Adeyemi and Osibajo (2013), examined the effect of e-HRM with emphasis on e-recruitment, e-performance and e-training, on organisational performance focusing on service delivery and commitment. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from 232 respondents from Guaranty Trust Bank, Lagos Nigeria and were analysed using Amos21 analysis tool. The study revealed that strong positive association exist amongst e-HRM variables and was in line with organisational performance variables. Further noted among others that, significant relationship exists between e-recruitment and service delivery, thereby accepting the study hypotheses.

The formulated hypothesis is:

H₀₁. There is no significant effect of e-HRM on organisational performance in the Nigerian brewery industry

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Model Specification:

$$OP = \beta_0 + \beta_1ER + \beta_2ET + \beta_3EP + \beta_4EC + e_1$$

$$OP = \theta_0 + \theta_1eHRM + \theta_2OC + e_2$$

Where:

$$OP = f(e-hrm)$$

OP = FP (Financial Perspective), CP (Customers Perspective), IP (Internal Perspective), LP

(Learning Perspective)

E-HRM = ER, ET, EP, EC

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Regression Coefficient

$\theta_1 - \theta_2$ = Regression Coefficient

e = error term

Methodology

This study is a case study design carried out within the Brewery industry of Nigeria. The population comprised middle and senior level management employees of the selected brewery firms which is 1,941. The selected Brewery firms are: Nigerian Breweries Plc and International Breweries Plc, within South-west region of Nigeria. The sample size was determined, using Slovin, (1960), which resulted to 332. The data was obtained through primary source with questionnaire as instrument. A total of 332 copies of questionnaire were administered to the respondents where 303 were returned which represented 94.09% of the total administered. The questionnaire survey questions covered demographics, e-HRM components and organizational performance perspectives on the respondents. The questions were framed to assess employees' perception on the extent to which they agree or disagree with the use and effect of e-HRM on organizational performance. The data collected was subjected to data cleaning procedure which removed 20 cases due to missing data and unengaged responses. Therefore the study used 283 certified copies of the questionnaire, which represented 93.3% of the returned copies of questionnaire.

Constructs were measured by many observed variables, which have been tested and confirmed in previous studies. The constructs in e-HRM were adapted from (Abiodun, *et al*, 2013) while in terms of organizational performance (OP), we adopted the model of Balanced Score Card (Kaplan & Norton, 1996). The study engaged both descriptive and inferential statistics to analyse the data. The descriptive was percentages on the demographics and charts on the perception of the employees while the inferential statistics considered Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Modelling (PLS –SEM), in the statistical software application SmartPls3.0 as the most appropriate tool, for it can estimate many relationships simultaneously and it is a frequently used multivariate analysis method in management science research (Hair; Hult; Sarstedt, 2017).

Findings

Demographic Information

Table 1. Demographic profile of the Respondents.

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	164	58.0
Female	119	42.0
Total	283	100.0
Age		
Below 20years	14	4.9
20-29 Years	112	39.6
30-39 Years	116	41.0
40-49 Years	31	11.0
50-Above	10	3.5
Total	283	100.0

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Marital Status		
Single	94	33.2
Married	185	65.4
Divorced	3	1.1
Separated	1	0.4
Total	283	100.0
Literacy Level		
Wassce/Gce	20	7.1
Nce/Ond	46	16.3
Hnd/B.Sc	132	46.6
Post Graduate	85	30.0
Total	283	100.0
Length Of Service In The Organization		
1-5years	155	54.8
6-10years	83	29.3
11-15years	28	9.9
16-20years	8	2.8
21 + Years	9	3.2
Total	283	100.0
Department Within The Organization		
Human Resource	78	27.6
Corporate Affairs	26	9.2
Production	65	23.0
General Administration	39	13.8
Sales & Distribution	19	6.7
It	18	6.4
Finance	26	9.2
Others/Specify	12	4.2
Total	283	100.0
Total	283	100.0

Employee's perception of the use of e-HRM (Components) in the organisation

Figure 2. Perception on e-recruitment

Figure 3. Perception on e-recruitment

Figure 4. Perception on e-training

Figure 5. Perception on e-training

Figure 6. Perception on e-performance system

Figure 7. Perception on e-performance system

8. Perception on e-compensation

9. Perception on e-compensation

Figure 2, revealed that staggering 94% of employees perceived e-recruitment enhances human resource service delivery. This perception is further solidified by the fact that 50% of the employees agreed, while an additional 45% strongly agreed. The dissenting voices were negligible, with less than one percent disagreeing and only 5 percent remaining undecided. From Figure 3, findings showed that 87% of the employees perceived that e-recruitment applications enhances cost reduction on recruitment activities. This perception is further solidified by 39% and 48% agreed and strongly agreed respectively. Whereas, less than one percent strongly disagree as 1% disagreed with 11% undecided.

Figure 4 reveals 87% of the employees perceived that e-training practices reduces training cost in the organisation as this is agreed by 39% and 49% strongly agreed, while less than 1% and 1% strongly disagreed and disagreed where 11% were undecided. Findings further revealed from figure 5 that, 89% of the employees perceived that e-training applications process improves human resource service delivery. This perception is further solidified by 40% agreed and 50% strongly agreed while 1% disagreed where no one strongly disagreed whereas only 10 were undecided.

Figure 6 further revealed 91% of the employees perceived that employees performance can be assessed for periodic result through the e-performance management systems. This is supported by 49% agreed and 42% strongly agreed to the perception, whereas 1% disagreed and none strongly disagreed as 8% were undecided, while figure 7 shows that 89% of the employees perceived that e-performance systems improves HR delivery through access to performance data. This is modified by 42% agreed and 48% strongly agreed, whereas less than 1% strongly disagreed and 1% disagreed where 9% were undecided.

Figure 8 revealed that, 88% of the employees perceived, e-compensation applications make payroll process more accurate. This perception is further solidified by 33% agreeing and 55% strongly agreed. Whereas, 1% strongly disagreed and 2% disagreed whereas 9% undecided while figure 9, revealed 86% of the employees perceived that compensation data are available in e-compensation application. This is further solidified by 35% agreed and 51% strongly agreed. The dissenting voices were negligible, with less than 2% disagreeing and 11 percent remaining undecided.

Assessing Measurement and Structural Models in PLS-SEM

The measurement model involves examining the indicator reliability, internal consistency (Composite reliability and Cronbach alpha), convergent validity (Average Variance Extracted AVE) and discriminant validity (Fornell-Larcker criterion and heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT)). PLS-SEM reflective measurement model was evaluated, the results are shown from Table 2 and Figure 10, the internal consistency reliability of the constructs are shown using, Cronbach's alpha (CA) , rho_A and Composite reliability. The results met up with the required values of reliability > 0.7 and AVE > 0.5

Table 2. Results of Internal Consistency and Convergent Validity for Effect of e-HRM on Organisational Performance

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
e-Compensation	0.796	0.797	0.860	0.552
e-Performance	0.774	0.783	0.848	0.528
e-Recruitment	0.778	0.786	0.850	0.532
e-Training	0.607	0.607	0.793	0.562
Customers Perspective	0.857	0.863	0.891	0.542
Learning Perspective	0.778	0.779	0.849	0.530
Financial Perspective	0.844	0.845	0.906	0.763
Internal Perspective	0.773	0.782	0.847	0.527

Figure 10. Measurement model for e-HRM on organisational performance

The discriminant validity was carried out using Fornell-Larcker criterion and Heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) criterion as provided by Hair et al. (2017). This is shown in Table.3&4.

Table 3. Fornell-Larcker Criterion Test for e-HRM and Organisational Performance

	EC	EP	ER	ET	CS	ES	FP	PI
EC	0.743							
EP	0.437	0.727						
ER	0.426	0.288	0.730					
ET	0.447	0.312	0.477	0.750				
CS	0.403	0.375	0.468	0.342	0.736			
ES	0.484	0.381	0.455	0.307	0.533	0.728		
FP	0.335	0.312	0.419	0.273	0.344	0.413	0.874	
PI	0.399	0.314	0.411	0.336	0.450	0.356	0.358	0.726

Table 4. HTMT Criterion test for e-HRM on Organisational Performance

	BEC	BEP	BER	BET	CCS	CES	CFP	CPI
BEC								
BEP	0.556							
BER	0.531	0.369						
BET	0.641	0.451	0.697					
CCS	0.489	0.467	0.566	0.473				
CES	0.615	0.492	0.572	0.444	0.652			
CFP	0.409	0.383	0.511	0.381	0.406	0.507		
CPI	0.503	0.399	0.518	0.477	0.543	0.455	0.447	

The structural model for e-HRM on organizational performance is shown with the determination of (R²) and the path coefficients. The R² value, measures the overall effects size and variance explained in the endogenous construct (dependent variable) by the exogenous constructs (independent variables). The R² is also referred to as in-sample predictive power (Rigdon, 2012).

Table 5 and Figure.11, showed the R² value is 0.477 for organisational performance (OP) endogenous latent construct. This indicates that the independent constructs explain 48% of the variance in OP, meaning that 48% of the change (variation) in organisational performance was due to the e-HRM practices that took place in the organization. The formulated hypothesis:

H01. There is no significant effect of e-HRM on organisational performance in the Nigerian brewery industry, was therefore rejected

The PLS-SEM result showed the relevance and significant level of the structural model relationship, the R-square and the effect size is shown in Table 5 and Figures 11 & 12, also showed the R-square on the path model.

Table 5. Testing of Hypothesis One Results

Hypothesised path	Beta	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics	p value	f square	R Square
b_HRM -c_PERF	0.690	0.039	17.491	0.000	0.910	0.477

Figure 11. Algorithm, Path Coefficient of e-HRM on Organisational Performance.

Figure 12. Bootstrapping of e-HRM on Organisational Performance

Figure 13. IPMA

Figure 14. IPMA

Figure 15. IPMA

Discussions

This study, revealed that e-HRM has a significant positive effect on Organisational Performance (OP) from the model $\beta = 0.690$, $t = 17.491$, $f^2 = 0.910$, $R^2 = 0.477$ and $P < 0.05$. The R-square of 0.477 indicates a predictive power of the outcome in the model as 48% variation in Organisational Performance is explained by e-HRM practices as shown in the identified components. This implies that for every unit increase in e-HRM components, Organisational Performance (OP) increase by 0.48. The R2 value could be viewed as combined effect of the exogenous variables on endogenous variables. It measures the variance in each endogenous construct for the structural model (Hussain et al., 2018). Moreover, according to Cohen (1988), an R2 value equal to 0.12 or below indicates low, values between 0.13 to 0.25 indicates medium and values of 0.26 or above indicate high effect size. The result in this study indicates a high effect size. The P value 0.000 less than 0.05 shows the significance effect of e-HRM on organizational performance. Furthermore, effect size (f^2) is the degree of the impact of each exogenous latent construct on the endogenous latent construct (Hussain et al., 2018). That is, when

an independent construct is deleted from the path model, the value of the coefficient of determination (R^2) is changed, and defines whether the removed latent construct has a significant influence on the endogenous latent construct. According to Cohen (1988), the f^2 values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 represent weak, moderate and strong effects respectively. The f^2 value of 0.910 in this study represent a strong impact.

This result is consistent with findings from previous studies (Rahman & Hosain, 2021; Thatrsaru & Sutha, 2021; Ahmed, 2019 and Abiodun, Adeyemi & Osibanjo, 2013) who found that there is a significant positive relationship between e-HRM and organisational performance. The results showed the relevance of e-HRM as a strategic tool that impacts organisational performance. The implication is that, the examined e-HRM components in this study should be strategically positioned within the organization in attaining performance.

The study further ascertained the degree of effect and relevance of the selected e-HRM components on organisational performance. PLS-SEM Importance –Performance Map analysis was carried out to determine the component with the strongest weight. The need for this is to strengthen the policy implications and the recommendations from this study.

Figures 13 and 14 (IPMA) showed the weight level to ascertain the most effective e-HRM component that the organisation can intentionally leverage on: e-Recruitment= 0.383, e-Training= 0.078, e-Performance System= 0.216, e-Compensation= 0.250. From the findings, it was revealed that e-recruitment has the strongest weight which represented the strongest effect on organisational performance. Figure 15 revealed the significance of each of the components separately as e-training was not positively significant as indicated in the p-value of 0.133. The implication is that the organisation should strengthen e-Recruitment exercises within the organisation and harness strategic organisational efforts to attain the values in e-Training. From the implications of IPMA analysis, all the components of e-HRM performed well in terms of their effects on organisational performance with e-Recruitment performed mostly.

Conclusion

This study has shown the perception of the employees' on the use and effect of e-HRM components on organizational performance to reveal some measure of impacts. The study further clarified the strongest component of e-HRM among the selected four which is e-Recruitment. This study only examined four selected e-HRM components within a sector in the Nigerian economy. The study has contributed to learning by showing the perception of employees on the use and effect of four identified e-HRM components on organizational performance in direct descriptive and empirical inferential patterns. The study has further contributed to the conceptual definition of e-HRM as: “The strategic application of digital technology innovations to the practice of human resource management within the organisation”.

Recommendations and Future Studies

This study therefore recommends that the use of e-HRM components, e-recruitment, e-training, e-performance and e-compensation as examined in this study should be deployed in the human resource process within corporate organisations as they have been seen to have positive significant relationship with organizational performance. The organization should maintain the necessary infrastructures that will enhance the progressive usage of the e-HRM components within the firms. Corporate organisations should place special emphasis on the strongest component of e-HRM among the selected four which is e-Recruitment. Implication is that the organisations should strengthen e-Recruitment exercise and strategically position e-HRM practices as corporate strategies to enhance organization performance. Further studies could be conducted on other identified e-HRM components like e-talent hunting, to know whether they could predict organizational performance. Such studies could be carried out in other sectors of the economy, like the manufacturing or service industries.

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